

GENE NAME	GENE ID	^(5') FORWARD PRIMER ^(3')	^(5') REVERSE PRIMER ^(3')
LDSP 3' UTR	-	GAGCTCGAAAGATCCAAGAGA GACGAG	CTTAAGGTGATGCTGTTGCTCTTTCC
EF PRO	-	CACCTATAGCTACATGGTAGC TAG	TGTTACGAAGTGAGGGTTGAG
VFP	-	GTTAACCAATTGGGGAGCGGC ATGGTGAGCAAGGGCGAG	ACGCGTAGGCCTGCCGCTTCCTTTG TACAACATCCATCCCAAGC
GFP	-	CGTAAACGGCCACAAGTTCA	CGCTTTACTTGTACAGCTCGT

Table S4. Primers used for amplification of sequences of *pnoc ox venus* vector and *pnoc gfp dgtt5pro* vector used for transformation of *N. oceanica* CCMP1779; LDSP; lipid droplet surface protein, EF; elongation factor, VFP; venus fluorescent protein, GFP; green fluorescent protein.